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Why Licensed Professional Teachers Deserve the Title “Tr.”

Titles influence how we view and value different professions. In daily life, they show competence, responsibility, and accountability. When we hear Dr., Atty., or Engr., we think of years of training, licensure, and ethical standards. Teachers, who help shape every other profession, deserve the same recognition.

That is why using “Tr.” simply stands for Teacher should be seriously considered as a title before the name of Licensed Professional Teachers (LPTs).

It is important to note that “Tr.” is only for LPTs. This title is used by people with formal qualifications. An LPT has finished the required education, passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers, and is committed to following the Code of Ethics set by the Professional Regulation Commission. The title is earned, not just given.

Some people might say that the LPT designation is enough. LPT is an important credential, but it is a title used after the name, mostly in official documents, records, and signatures. In daily school life, like in classrooms, meetings, or introductions, these titles are rarely used or noticed.

A title before the name works differently. When someone is called “Tr. Santos” or “Tr. Dela Cruz,” it is clear right away that they are a professional teacher. This title brings the idea of licensure into daily school life, where respect and authority are built through everyday interactions. In this way, “Tr.” turns the LPT credential into something people see and use every day.

Allowing only LPTs to use “Tr.” helps protect the profession’s integrity. It sets licensed teachers apart from those in informal or unregulated roles. Not everyone who teaches is a professional teacher, just as not everyone who gives legal advice is an attorney. The title “Tr.” shows regulation, accountability, and responsibility.

Titles are not just symbols. In schools and universities, they help set professional boundaries and build respect. The way teachers are addressed shapes how students see the profession. Using “Tr.” shows that teaching is serious, skilled work, guided by standards, ethics, and public trust.

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Using a professional title for licensed teachers sends a strong message about how much society values education. Teachers help build the nation by shaping minds, values, and future leaders. Still, teaching has often been undervalued, even though it is vital for national growth. Giving licensed teachers a clear, visible title helps fix this and puts teaching on the same level as other licensed professions.

In the end, the difference is simple but important. LPT shows legal qualification, while “Tr.” shows that qualification in daily life. They do not compete with each other; they work together.

“Tr.” stands for Teacher, but it means a teacher who is licensed, professional, and accountable.

For this reason, if someone is an LPT, the title “Tr.” is not only appropriate but also deserved.